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PROBLEM OF COMMUNICATIVE TOLERANCE IN PROFESSIONAL EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITIES OF A TEACHER

Проблема комунікативної толерантності в професійній педагогічній діяльності вчителя

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Abstract

The article deals with the problem of communicative tolerance in the professional pedagogical activity of teacher in establishments of higher educational. The aim and essence, its structure, stages and ways of realization in the pedagogical activity are researched in it.

Key words: *professional pedagogical activity, communicative tolerance, educational content, conditions of teaching, effectiveness of studies.*

Introduction

The globalization and integration country, of world association and European community contributes of to the rapid growth of the role of quality education for the further development of society, and in accordance its intensive reform. Given this problem actualized improve the quality of process of preparation the future teachers, including of problem of communicative tolerance in professional pedagogical activity of teacher, its require of process to effective realization of competence approach. Effective deciding of these tasks possible for conditions by the improvement of educational content and its procedural-methodical using on innovation basis. The quality of professional preparation of future teachers depends of the content to modern education, it should include of full orientation on purchase by students' of system the competencies and permanent updating by improving the mechanisms and their using in everyday practice.

Ukraine wishes to commit to the European dimension of higher education by adopting measures from the Bologna Declaration. At the same time, certain issues relating to the Bologna Process objectives remain to be addressed. One of the issues is to develop learners' professional language competence.

The democratic and humanization reforms which take place in Ukraine need renovating the process of teaching foreign languages, recomprehending aims, tasks and contents of education, implementation of new educational technologies to master foreign communicative competence successfully.

In conditions of socio-political and economic instability of modern Ukrainian society much of the population has lost moral and ethical guidelines, instead of it deepened the insecurity that led to general psychological strain in relations between people. Such degradation can be traced primarily in aversion to each other, the political elite and state as a whole.

In this regard actualized the problem of formation and development of communicative tolerance of every conscious citizen, younger generation, and young people, regardless of social status, gender or ethno characteristic.

Communicative tolerance is a core characteristic of the individual, because it largely determines the life and work (the situation in the immediate vicinity, at work, in career advancement, professional capacity). Communicative tolerance as an integral quality of a teacher is manifested in the structure of his professional educational activities.

Research methods

Methods of theoretical generalization, analysis of theoretical literature, meta-analysis, and system analysis are used in the article.

Results

Analysis of last researches and publications from problems of the research showed, that there is significant world theoretical and practical improvements in the field of competence approach in the process of preparation of future teacher. By many scientists of Ukraine are considered the problem of forming of competence the specialists of different profiles. In particular, explored the problem of formation of professional pedagogical competence of teachers (N. Borytko, S. Demchenko,

L. Zelenska, I. Mishchenko, R. Serozhnykova); professional competence of officers (O. Vorontsov); pedagogical competence of teachers (L. Golik, N. Loseva, A. Shyszko); psychological-pedagogical competence of teachers (N.Lisova) and others.

As a result of thorough theoretical and methodological analysis of forms and features in display of communicative tolerance/intolerance were singled out the factors, orientation on which determines communicative tolerance of a teacher:

- knowledge of oneself (tolerant man is well-versed in his/her own advantages and disadvantages);
- protection (a sense of security and confidence);
- responsibility (internal locus of control);
- the need for certainty;
- targeting over himself (mainly targeting on personal independence, less - to belonging to external institutions and authorities);
- lack of absolute adherence to rules (low pedantry);
- the ability for empathy;
- sense of humor;
- favoring for freedom and democracy.

Therefore, based on the singled factors which ensure tolerant personality's development it is possible to formulated principles of tolerant relationship in communication of a teacher with students:

- rejection from violence as an unacceptable means of familiarizing the younger generation to any idea;
- voluntary choice in behavior;
- ability to force myself not forcing others;
- compliance to laws, respect for traditions and customs;
- another decision that may differ on various grounds – ethnic, racial, cultural, religious and other.

In the process of dialogue training the students learn: to solve complex problems on the basis of analyzing the circumstances and corresponding information, to consider alternative opinions, to take well-considered decisions, to take part in discussions, to associate with different people (Martinelli, 2000).

It's necessary to organize different forms of activity at the foreign language group that is individual, pair, and team. Among the most well known form of pair and group work the following kinds should be mentioned: inside (outside) circles, brain

storm, line-ups, jigsaw reading, think-pair-share, debate, pair-interviews etc. E.g., jigsaw reading is an activity which involves the splitting of a text into different parts or the use of different texts on the same topic. The parts are given to different learners to read. They must communicate with each other in order to find out the whole message or different views on the topic.

It is necessary to point out that all above-mentioned form of interactive training is efficient in case a problem is discussed as a whole in the students have previous experience and ideas which they have acquired earlier at their classes or in a course of their private life. In the process of work the teacher should take into consideration the fact that the topics which are to be discussed in the classroom must not be limited or very narrow. One of the most common peculiarities which are characteristic of the interactive forms are those that these forms of training motivate the student not only to express their own opinion but after some argumentation of their partners in the process of work to change the point of view (Ruchen, 2003: 26).

There is a variety of intolerance generating sources in our society today, e.g. violence, cruelty, alienation. Formation of teacher's communicative tolerance should be seen as paramount urgent task if we want to save the country, society, man and humanity.

Conclusions

In view of the fact that in Europe in one form or another the designated issues have been discussing during five centuries, and this process is imprinted in the minds of Europeans, we using their experience, cannot and should not blindly copy it. Formation of communicative teacher's tolerance must be built on the basis of our ethno-mental realities, features of traditions and culture, and the most importantly – people's minds readiness to specific changes.

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